

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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XORIJIY TAJRIBA**

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KIRISH SO‘ZI

HURMATLI ANJUMAN ISHTIROKCHILARI, MEHMONLAR, HAMKASBLAR, AZIZ TALABALAR!

Sizlarni Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot instituti tomonidan tashkil etilayotgan mazkur Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumanida qutlashdan mamnunmiz.

Qadrli anjuman ishtirokchilari, bugun biz mamlakatimizda biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish masalalari bo‘yicha amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo‘llari, hamda bu yo‘nalishdagi xorijiy tajribalarni muhokama qilish uchun to‘plandik.

Habaringiz bor, Prezidentimiz tomonidan 2024-yilni O‘zbekistonda “Yoshlar va biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash yili”, deb e‘lon qilinganida, inson qadrini ulug‘lash va aholimiz manfaatlarini ta‘minlash uchun kuchli iqtisodiyot barpo etish asosiy vazifalarimizdan biri ekanligi ta‘kidlangan edi.

Shunga ko‘ra, joriy yilda iqtisodiyotimizga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishga, tadbirkorlik va xususiy mulk uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratishga, ilm-fan, innovatsiya, IT kabi sohalarni, “yashil” va raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga alohida e‘tibor qaratilmoqda.

Chunki, barqaror va kuchli iqtisodiyot nafaqat iqtisodiyot subyektlari uchun, balki jamiyatimizning kelajagi va farovonligi uchun ham juda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Hozirgi kunda, bizning jamiyatimiz - raqamli transformatsiya davriga qadam qo‘ydi. Raqamlashtirish jarayoni - biznes jarayonlaridan tortib, davlat xizmatlariga qadar ko‘plab sohalarni qamrab olmoqda.

Albatta bunday o‘zgarishlar, texnologik taraqqiyotga hamohang ravishda, qo‘shimcha imkoniyatlarni ochishga va rivojlanishning yangi strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishga keng imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda.

Lekin shu bilan bir qatorda, iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish va bunday sharoitda biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida, o‘ziga xos muammolar va turli savollar ham yuzaga kelmoqda.

Bunday masalalarni o‘rganib, uning yechimlarini topish uchun Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot institutining professor-o‘qituvchilari tomonidan ham turli ilmiy tadqiqotlarni olib borish yo‘lga qo‘yilgan. Ularning tadqiqotlari natijalaridan - o‘quv jarayonlarida, ta‘lim sifatini oshirish maqsadlarida, keng foydalaniladi.

Bu o‘z navbatida, institutda menejment, iqtisodiyot va axborot texnologiyalari sohasida tayyorlanadigan malakali mutaxassislarining nafaqat nazariy bilimlarini, balki amaliy ko‘nikmalarini ham oshirishga hizmat qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, institutda innovatsion dasturlar va loyihalar orqali talabalarni yangi texnologiyalar bilan tanishtirish, ularda raqamli iqtisodiyot va global biznes muhitida raqobatbardosh bo‘lish uchun zarur bo‘lgan ko‘nikmalarni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Bugungi anjumanda, biz raqamlashtirish va biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida uchraydigan muammolarni chuqur o‘rganishni va ilmiy asoslangan yechimlarni izlashni o‘z oldimizga maqsad qilib qo‘yganmiz.

Shu bilan birga, asosiy anjuman va sho‘ba yig‘ilishlarida mazkur masalalar bo‘yicha xorijiy tajribalarni ham tahlil qilish orqali, biz qanday yechimlar topishimiz mumkinligini muhokama qilamiz.

Bugun sizlarning e‘tiboringizga taqdim etiladigan taqdimotlar va fikrlar - bizni zamonaviy iqtisodiyotning yangi talablariga mos keladigan biznes modellarni yaratishga ilhomlantiradi.

Maqsadimiz – bu kabi ilmiy-amaliy uchrashuvlar orqali ilm ahlini va biznes vakillarini bir joyda jamlab, biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini hamda iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish jarayonlarini yanada takomillashtirish bo‘yicha asoslangan takliflar va amaliy tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqishga imkoniyatlar yaratishdan iboratdir.

Biz bu jarayonda, o‘z tajribamizni almashish va birgalikda muammolarni hal qilish uchun yangi g‘oyalarni kashf etishni maqsad qilamiz.

Umid qilamanki, anjumanimiz samarali va foydali bo‘ladi.

Har biringizning ishtirokingiz va hissangiz bu jarayonda juda muhim.

Keling, birgalikda yangiliklarga ochiq bo‘lib, innovatsion yechimlarni izlaylik!

Bugungi anjuman ishiga va unda ishtirok etayotgan barcha ishtirokchilarning ilmiy-ijodiy faoliyatlariga ulkan muvaffaqiyatlar tilaymiz!

**Axmedov Xojiakbarxon Dilshatovich,
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5-SHO'BA.
BIZNES VA BOSHQARUVDA RAQAMLI
IQTISODIYOT HAMDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT
TEXNOLOGIYALARI

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DIGITAL PLATFORMS IN THE SYSTEMATIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Digitalization of the national economy implies the active introduction of modern information technologies and new business models. The digital economy creates new economic laws by erasing the boundaries between digital and real life based on the convergence of business processes, technologies, objects and virtual space. In such conditions, there is a need to introduce a digital ecosystem that integrates digital platforms, digital infrastructure and digital solutions.

According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-14 of November 17, 2021, a «roadmap» was drawn up for the establishment of an «Open Digital Ecosystem» in order to improve the administration of e-commerce and create favorable conditions for its further development¹. According to this:

- forming a digital ecosystem and performing the functions of its operator;
- to create conditions for e-commerce platforms to use their customer base equally and provide services to them, regardless of the form of ownership, departmental and network affiliation, territorial location;
- in connection with the execution of the functions of the «escrow» system of the digital ecosystem, it is planned to implement the goals and tasks such as calculations and payments from one personal account and ensuring the contractual obligations of the parties are guaranteed (according to the letter of credit).

Thus, the main task of using digital platforms is to create conditions for favorable interaction between all participants of digital solutions by forming a single digital ecosystem.

The digital ecosystem should be accessible to consumers, suppliers and government or businesses and organizations themselves. In order to attract suppliers of digital resources, programs should be developed to encourage participation in the digital ecosystem, which will give digitalization entities not only the planned financial result, but also the opportunity to strengthen competitive advantages, strengthen the brand position or the reputation of the organization, increase efficiency or receive other intangible benefits. Interactions with various digital platforms expand the boundaries of the organization's activity, forcing it to look for new opportunities and use them without being limited to a certain field of activity. This creates a new level of value creation and delivery to consumers. The participation of consumers of digital resources in the work of the digital ecosystem allows them not only to save money or time resources to purchase the necessary goods or services without intermediaries, but also to acquire new knowledge and skills, increase their status and self-esteem, in the global network of relations between people, organizations and government bodies. a sense of social importance and participation. Modern consumers quickly get used to the achieved level of digital services and demand new solutions that meet their needs with a high level of service quality and personalization, taking into account the individual characteristics and interests of a particular consumer.

The digital ecosystem serves to enable a large part of the population to actively use ICT, to radically increase the efficiency of business and government activities, and to introduce an effective management system by creating digital innovations. In this case, we suggest paying special attention to the following processes:

First, it is necessary to introduce digital platforms covering all sectors of the economy in order to increase the speed of information exchange between different parties at the international and national level.

Today, comprehensive measures are being implemented in Uzbekistan for the active development of the digital economy, as well as the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies to all sectors, primarily public administration, education, health care and agriculture. Therefore, within the framework of the implementation of the «Digital Uzbekistan - 2030» strategy, which is to create a full-fledged digital environment and digital space in the republic, a number of programs for digitization of various sectors

¹ Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 17, 2021 No. PQ-14 "On improving the administration of electronic commerce and creating favorable conditions for its further development". URL: <https://lex.uz/acts/5732739>.

of our country have been developed. In addition, a number of legal frameworks for the development of the digital economy and its regulation have been created in our country (see Appendix 1). Nevertheless, global digital development is gaining momentum and this process is creating complex competition between different countries. In particular, according to the ICT development index, Uzbekistan ranks 103rd among more than 170 countries, ahead of Egypt, but behind Turkey and Brazil. If in 2021 the number of Internet users per 100 permanent residents was 65.8 units, then in 2022 this indicator was 75.0 units. Although these indicators have a growing trend, they are not enough for global competition at the world level².

In overcoming these problems, it is important to introduce digital platforms based on the experience of leading countries worldwide. In particular, the use of digital platforms provides the following advantages:

- by encouraging innovation, it provides an opportunity to create new digital programs;
- creates new consumer value;
- expands market opportunities and leads to an increase in the variety of goods, products and services;
- reduces transaction costs,
- allows to increase the well-being and quality of life of the population.

At the heart of digital transformation lies the challenge of creating a digital environment that encourages legal and physical entities to interact with each other. Thus, a digital platform is a structure that allows managing digital processes between suppliers, partners and consumers in a unified environment. Therefore, the concept of "digital platform" is not limited to certain technological trends (for example, cloud technologies, "big" data, artificial intelligence, blockchain, Internet of things, etc.), but is based on the interaction of various digital tools, constantly changing to meet the needs of consumers. includes high-tech solutions.

With the development of digital technologies, the efficiency of mass production of the same type has decreased dramatically, giving way to customized production, the introduction of digital household services and the formation of integrated ecosystems of interactions with customers. The economic importance of digital platforms is determined by ensuring the attractiveness of new business models for the development of small and medium-sized businesses, because electronic platforms allow the use of innovative resources of state authorities, large enterprises and organizations to achieve economic development of the country. Digital platforms make it possible to reduce transaction costs in various industries, create reliable and fast communications, optimize business processes, create conditions for economic development and create new ways of creating value for consumers, while reducing the dependence of economic entities on the environment.

In recent years, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, through the development of digital government and the implementation of state programs in this regard, the need to create electronic platforms for establishing mutual reliable communication with business entities and residents, monitoring the socio-economic situation in the region is increasing. Due to the impact on the economy of the consequences of the pandemic in 2020, such as restrictions on social communication, new opportunities are opening up for the use of electronic platforms in post-pandemic conditions, including the creation of a single regional information space, the provision of stable growth of economic indicators, and the wide opening of the social and entrepreneurial potential of organizations and residents of the region. serves.

The advantages of digital platforms in the development of the digital economy include:

- unites various economic entities in one place, which determines the high speed and quality of management decision-making for the development of business activity;
- provides an opportunity to integrate new functional modules into the existing platform that arise due to changes in the needs of socio-economic development over time;
- in contrast to traditional business, reducing the fixed costs of the enterprise, not by expanding production capabilities, but by using modern digital solutions, reduces production costs depending on the volume of demand;
- reduces transaction costs by eliminating intermediaries between service providers, producers and consumers;
- increases the profitability of the network user by increasing the use of the digital platform;
- the quality of goods and services on digital platforms is determined by the large number of users that belong to it, which increases the interest of interested parties and, as a result, the opportunity to earn income in a short time.

In addition, the introduction of digital platforms creates conditions for innovative development and various digital dividends. They take the foundations of traditional economics to a new level, serving to reduce cross-border costs in various market relations on a global scale. In particular, the conditions for wide coverage of customers for enterprises and organizations are created.

2 Thomas Rittera, Carsten Lund Pedersena (2020) «Digitization capability and the digitalization of business models in business-to-business firms: Past, present, and future» - *Industrial Marketing Management* 86, p. 180-190.

Among the digital platforms, the only portal that gathers all government services in one place; information exchange platforms that allow interaction between public and private enterprises and organizations, as well as parties; mobile application development platforms;

common services platforms related to digital identity and authentication, digital money transfers and digital commerce can be distinguished.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, digital government platforms are being actively developed for the purpose of using public services. The interaction of individuals and legal entities with state bodies through an electronic portal, that is, the provision of electronic state services by the government, is an integral part of the digital economy. For this purpose, the Single Interactive State Services Portal (Single Portal) has been operating³. According to the latest statistics, the number of applications received from the Single portal has reached 12.8 million. The number of services launched on the single portal has reached 650. 88% of users are between 18 and 54 years old⁴. It can be seen that despite the fact that the portal of electronic public services has been introduced a lot, it is actively used by the population.

Secondly, the increasing number of cross-border electronic transactions between users and business entities at the international level creates the need to create new digital solutions, in particular, single integrated electronic open trade zones. In addition, digital solutions cover finance, customs services, procurement, taxation, logistics and population migration, simplify trade procedures and create conditions for increasing digital dividends.

Examples of such solutions include the creation of verified, official and reliable sources of the following main registers:

- basic information about citizens, enterprises, companies;
- basic information about vehicles, licenses, land plots,
- basic information about buildings, settlements and roads⁵.

Figure 1. The model of introduction of digital platforms in the systematic development of the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan⁶

3 See: www.my.gov.uz.

4 URL: <https://my.gov.uz/uz/site/statistic> (as of 04.07.2024).

5 L.V. Lapidus. Digital Economy: A textbook for bachelors and masters in the fields of "Economics" and "Management". - M.: 2018. - 30 p.

6 Muallif ishlanmasi.

It is also important to focus on digital solutions in cross-border public procurement. The signing of multilateral agreements based on public procurement reduces the difference between the share of imports of the member states of the agreement in public and private consumption. According to the European Directorate General of Trade (“DG Trade”), a 50% decrease in the share of imports will lead to an increase of 0.01% in the GDP of the participating countries.

Digital commerce, customs and export-related digital solutions include facilitating the import and export of goods and services, as well as logistics and licensing issues. In particular, the «single window» that gathers the government bodies responsible for the implementation of the import and export process in one place allows you to submit the necessary documents in electronic form from anywhere.

To summary, implementing digital platforms for the systematic development of the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the actual task for the government. It is highly important to upgrade the digital infrastructure in the country in order to achieve digital goals.

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